

85 wet seasons relating yield to agronomic traits of rainfed lowland breeding lines. Water depth was maintained at 25 to 50 cm from 3 wk after transplanting to maturity. We tested 75 entries in 1983, 73 in 1984, and 64 in 1985. They included check cultivars and advanced breeding lines, with entry changes each year.

Grain yields were low in 1983 and 1984 (0.6-3.0 t/ha), but were as high as 4.9 t/ha in 1985. They did not correlate well with agronomic traits. In 1984, a

subset of 25 entries was grown under shallow (5 cm) water depth. Grain yield for medium deepwater and shallow conditions correlated positively ($r = 0.66$), indicating that yield potential at both water depths was related. Tillering did not correlate with yield nor differ between depths. Plant heights averaged 138 cm over all entries under medium deep conditions, compared to 131 cm under shallow conditions. Average lodging score by *Standard evaluation*

system for rice (SES) was 5.5 in medium deepwater and 2.6 in shallow water.

Twenty-one breeding lines were included in all years' trials. Correlations between years were low. Several breeding lines performed better than check cultivars (see table).

In selecting lines for medium deep conditions, it is important to conduct yield trials over several years and select for intermediate plant height and lodging resistance. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Spikelet sterility in three rice cultivars

V. D. Naidu and P. S. Reddy, *Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Nellore 524004, A.P., India*

Spikelet deformity was observed in three rice cultivars at ARS farm in rabi 1983 (Oct-Mar), late rabi 1984-85 (Feb-Jun), and rabi 1985-86. Sterility ranged from 4 to 29%. When panicles were opened at booting, the androecium and gynoecium were already aborted and the lemma

and palea in florets were twisted. Most florets were aborted (see figure).

IR20 in rabi 1983, and Rasi and IR50 in late rabi 1984-85 and 1985-86 were

observed for sterility in the field. IR20 recorded 4.3%; Rasi, 28.8%; and IR50, 15.2% sterility (see table). The suspected cause of the high sterility in IR50 is high temperature from panicle initiation to flowering. The higher temperatures might have affected meiosis, resulting in sterility. □

Spikelet sterility in 3 rice cultivars and weather parameters during panicle initiation to flowering. ARS, Nellore, India, 1983-86.

Cultivar	Hills affected (%)	Panicles affected (%)	Total spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Weather parameter ^a		
					Maximum temp (°C)	Minimum temp (°C)	Relative humidity (%)
IR20	100	100	134.5	4.3	28.9	21.1	85.1
IR50	100	90	76.5	28.8	38.1	26.9	71.8
Rasi	100	100	66.4	15.2	37.0	26.0	70.3

^a Rainfall was nil during the trials.

Characteristics of sterile spikelets under high temperature at panicle initiation.

Hybrid rice responses to high temperature at flowering

Tan Zhonghe, Lan Taiyuan, and Fang Wen, *Sichuan Academy of Agricultural Sciences; and Ren Chang Fu, Southwestern Agricultural University, China*

We studied hybrid rice responses to high temperature at flowering in the phytotron and under natural climatic conditions in southeastern Sichuan, China. Panicles of hybrids Shan You 2 and Ai You 2 that emerged 50-60% at the same growth stage were observed. Before temperature treatments, spikelets that had undergone anthesis were cut. After treatment, unbloomed spikelets were cut.

In the phytotron, spikelets treated with a constant day temperature of 27, 29, 31, 33, 35, 37, and 39 °C for 6 consecutive hours from 0800 to 1400 h had sterility percentages of 10.0, 11.5, 7.7, 9.2, 15.8, 26.4, and 74.3%, respectively. Thus the percentage of sterility increased as temperature increased beyond 35 °C, a correlation significant at 1% level.

Sustaining the high temperature progressively increased sterility. Sterility was 15.5, 26.6, and 28.8% when the spikelets were treated at 35 °C for 2, 4, and 6 h, respectively.

Spikelet sterility induced by natural climatic high temperature was observed during flowering in fields in southeastern Sichuan, China. Results (see table)